

Designing reservist cells in time of crisis

Keywords: designing for emergencies, scenario design, emergent futures, stakeholder mapping

1. Abstract

Recent situations have illustrated the need for a more resilient population in times of crisis. In this workshop we introduce the concept of *Reservist cells* as a *network of stakeholders ready to act when emergencies are declared* and we invite the audience to envision together what would be the configurations of such networks through diverse emergency crises. As part of the [Reservist project](#), the team of Fab Lab Barcelona will guide the participants to play with a customized version of the [Atlas of Weak Signals](#) tool. This short online workshop will be a co-creation playground for designers who want to explore emergent futures and debate on new forms of design research that can foster glocal resilience.

2. Workshop Organisers

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2. Context and Aim of Workshop

Pandemics such Covid19 illustrate the need to have a population resilient in times of crisis. It is helping us to understand how our daily practices could change as well as how important it is to better anticipate which networks to create at different scales to face the scarcity of resources, products and services and let people have easy and fair access to basic commodities.

On top of the emergence of more distributed approaches exploring how to better live and produce in proximity areas (i-e from 1km to 15km cities to regions) (Manzini, 2022), preventive measures are being designed for better crisis management. The concept of “Reservist cells” takes its origin in the military and sanitary context to create a set of people ready to act when emergencies are declared. They are generally framed at the national or european scale. In the EU project Reservist (Reservist, 2020), the “reservist cells” concept is applied to the industrial context and experimented with a set of (industrial) stakeholders. Here we would like to go one step further and envision what would be and how would work the “reservist cell network” in a post-industrial context, that could be deployed in local areas to respond to local needs and product demands occurring in time of crisis.

Designing for future scenarios is not new. Recently, more practical approaches are explored, mixing prospective thinking with concrete actions, looping by design interventions to foster more tangible knowledge on what the future looks like. At Fab Lab Barcelona (2021), a Master in Design for Emergent Futures has been created since 2019 as *“a multidisciplinary design course which trains students to propose small-scale interventions to approach large-scale challenges”*. One course named *“atlas of weak signals”* is experimented and used as a tool to guide the students in their exploration of future trends (Diez et al., 2020).

For the Reservist project, we have been customizing the Atlas of Weak Signal so it permits participants to explore in a playful way diverse situations of crisis (natural and man-made disasters, pandemics, wars, black-outs...), diverse types of networks, different risks (logistics, supply, civil resistances...) and areas of opportunities (technical, platforms, services, policies..).

This workshop would allow DRS participants to discover this tool and to let the community discuss the concept of “Reservist” while shaping various scenarios of uses. They will reflect and debate on the role and practice of design research for short-term and long-term adaptation to crisis.

3. Planned Activities and Expected Outcomes

Workshop Length. The workshop will be a 1,5 hours workshop. 20-30 participants

Organization, Activities and Outcomes.

- Welcome & Inspirational talks (15mn): a presentation to all which introduces the participants to the concept of reservist cell, the creative environment of design tools and related projects led by the maker community .
- Discovery exercise of the Atlas of Weak Signal. (15mn): participants will have the possibility to quickly see the potential of the tool by creating their own design scenario, guided by one of the facilitators.
- Application with 3-4 types of crisis scenarios in breakout rooms (45mn): 3-4 board spaces will be created and 4 team groups of 5 will play independently. Each will face one type of crisis and imagine diverse agencements of Reservist cells, stimulated by alerts and opportunities.
- Wrap-up and feedback (15mn): Each team presents their scenario and how the Reservist cells they created would answer the crisis. Lastly, participants will have a space on the Miro to express the lessons learnt and reflect on current design research practices.

Participants will have the opportunity to apply divergent and long-term thinking.

4. Intended Audience

The workshop is for DRS participants who want to *engage by action* with current societal crises and are curious to play with emergent scenarios. Conference participants will work side by side with some partners of the Reservist consortium and external members of the Fab Lab community, involved in the Distributed Design Market Platform and the Fab City movement. Promising synergies could be provoked in the workshop.

Participants will be asked to sign an online consent form for sharing their contributions to the current research activities of the Reservist project.

5. Space and Equipment Required

We will be held in an online setting. Workshop team will supply the online co-creation tool and promote the use of the video conferencing system proposed by the conference. A local room with a screen could be needed in case facilitators are present in Bilbao during the conference.

6. Potential Outputs

The co-created concepts and the discussions will feed the reflections of design researchers as well as activities of the Reservist project. The content will be analyzed and synthesized into a book delivered for the end of the year 2022. The results will be disseminated into the wide network of makers via Fab Lab Barcelona's channels.

6. Acknowledgement

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7. References

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Manzini, E. (2022). *Livable Proximity: Ideas for the City that Cares*. EGEA spa.

Fab Lab Barcelona. (2022.). Project website. <https://fablabbcn.org/projects>

Reservist. (2022). Project. <https://cov-reservist.eu/project/>

Miro board link to copy the tools

https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVOWQSV7I=?share_link_id=244929389351

Resilient Makers Stories. <https://fablabbcn.org/blog/make-things/resilient-maker-stories>

About the Organisers:

Dr Marion Real, is a systemic design researcher at Fab Lab Barcelona, now in charge of the Reservist project. She has carried out workshops with companies, consultancy agencies and research centres during her PhD and facilitated many multi-stakeholder design processes for various European projects (RETRACE, SISCODE).

Mariana Quintero is Multimedia developer, interaction designer & researcher, Mariana Quintero works and develops her practice at IAAC Fab Lab Barcelona. She is actively involved in the Master in Design for Emergent Futures and running the Atlas of Weak Signals tool workshops in diverse contexts.

Jean Luc Pierite is a current student in the MDEF program. Now elected to the North American Indian Center of Boston Board of Directors, he was the International Procurement and Logistics Manager for The Fab Foundation with a strong background in graphic design and community management.